

PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENT OF CHEMICAL AND MINERALOGICAL COMPOSITION OF
BLACK COTTON SOILS IN NGURORE – NUMAN AREA, NORTHEASTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

An assessment of chemical and mineralogical composition of Black Cotton soils in parts of Ngurore – Numan areas of Yola basin, Nigeria was carried out using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometric and X – ray diffractometric methods. Samples from weathered basaltic rocks have high SiO₂ (48.7 – 54.7%), Al₂O₃ (16.1 – 19.8%) and Fe₂O₃ (1.7 – 4.2%) and those from weathered shale rocks show relatively high montmorillonite clay mineral, CaO (0.9 – 1.9%), MgO (1.6 – 4.6%), Na₂O (0.5 – 1.6%) and K₂O (0.1 – 0.7%) contents. The low composite sodium content (ave. 0.9%) of the studied cotton soils makes them unsuitable for use as drilling mud, but the appreciably high Ca, Mg and montmorillonite (89%) contents qualify them for use as decolorizing and purifying materials.

Key Words: Black cotton soil, Ngurore – Numan, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

There are extensive outcrops of black cotton soils in the Gongola and Yola basins of the Upper Benue valley. The outcrops belong to the class of superficial deposits closely associated with river alluvium, and known to overlie the Cretaceous marine sediments and Tertiary basalts. The weathering of basaltic rocks and clayey shales formed the soils, which are black to dark gray in colour. Black cotton soils are described as heavy cracking soils containing over 30% clay materials with high expanding clay minerals (or smectite) contents (Fanning and Fanning, 1989). They are hard when dry, become plastic and sticky when wet, and swell on wetting and shrink on drying. They are generally classified as montmorillonitic clays as the constituent clay minerals are dominated by montmorillonite. These montmorillonitic soils are known to form by weathering processes under alkaline conditions in the presence of magnesium. Ehlman (1968) reported that montmorillonitic clay and secondary clay vermiculite are formed from altered products of weathered basic volcanic rocks (e.g. basalts) in arid regions with low rainfall and limited leaching.

Montmorillonitic clays have high proportion of very fine particle sizes and highly hydrated colloidal fractions. Due to these inherent properties, presence of montmorillonite in industrial materials generally increases the dry strength of their products. Structurally, montmorillonitic clays have 2:1 layers (consisting of two tetrahedral sheets with an octahedral sheet between them), which allow for isomorphous substitution in the sheets, hence interlayer swelling of the structure (Grim, 1962). In addition, this expansive structure makes the clay material readily dispersible in water and strongly adsorptive. Their high colloidal, plastic and binding properties make them suitable for bonding molding sands, while their high swelling, cation exchange capacities, strong adsorptive powers and dispersibility in water makes them useful as drilling mud, and as oil decolorizer. Industrially, montmorillonitic clays have high commercial value.

In the Yola sub-basin of the Upper Benue valley, black cotton soils occur at Ngurore, Hossere, Bembel, Farri, Numan, Ngalang, Kwapukai, Kola, Banjiram, Talum and at Song in the southern tip of the Hawal Massif. Apart from the works of Carter et al (1963), no studies have been conducted on these deposits in the Yola area. In this study, outcrops at Hossere-Bembel, Ngalang and Kwapukai were investigated with the aim of characterizing the chemical and mineralogical compositions of the cotton soils, appraising lithologic influences on their occurrence and assessing their industrial suitability.

Location and Geology of Study area

The Ngurore – Numan area is located within the semi-arid region of northeastern Nigeria, between longitudes 11°55' and 12°15' E and latitudes 9°16' and 9°34' N (Fig 1). It covers an area of about 34.4sqkm². Lithologically, the area is mainly covered by old-terraced alluvium (consisting of shale, mudstone and clay) with five basaltic plugs interspersed at Ngurore, Sabana, Hoserre Bembel, Kwana Kuka and Kola, and Bima sandstone in the southeastern tip of the study area (Fig. 1). The Hossere-Bembel soil occurs in the vicinity (approximately 200m away from the foot) of a big extensively exploited basaltic volcanic plug (Ntekim & Adekeye, 2003), and adjoins a rock milling plant where tailings of the crushed basaltic chippings and construction powder are dumped, and is therefore representative of cotton soils formed from weathering of basaltic rocks. The Ngbalang and Kwapukai soils are found in areas within 1.5km away from the Benue River shores; an area covered by the dark old terraced alluvium, and not near to any of the volcanic plug, and is therefore representative of those formed from weathering of shaly sediments. Locally, the study area is marked by gently sloping to flat low-lying topography covered by weathered superficial debris characteristic of alluvial environment. Few rivers, majority of which are seasonal, drain intervening depressions.

Geologically, the study area lies within the Yola Arm of the Upper Benue valley, which comprises the Cretaceous Bima Sandstone and Yolde Formation, the Tertiary basaltic rocks and the Quaternary alluvium. According to Carter et al (1963) and Allix et al (1981), the Bima Sandstone is an Upper Aptian – Lower Albian Formation consisting of massive coarse grained sandstone beds, which are sometimes silicified and interbedded with shale, rare bands of calcareous sandstones and thin limestone laminations. The Yolde Formation unconformably overlies the Bima Sandstone and consists of interbedded sandstone and shale units. The Old terraced and Recent river alluvium constitutes the Quaternary rocks; which outcrop between hilly regions and the river courses, and along the flood plains of River Benue respectively. The Old terraced alluvium consists of mainly black to dark grey clayey shale while the characteristic Benue valley Recent alluvium consist of poorly sorted sand, siltstones and clays.

SAMPLING AND ANALYTICAL METHODS

i) Sampling

Five cotton soil samples were collected from locations A and B in the vicinity of the Hossere Bembel basaltic outcrop (Fig 1). Location A is a 250m² expanse of land adjacent to the Afcott Ginnery factory along Yola – Numan road and opposite the basaltic plug; while location B lies adjacent to the volcanic plug. At Ngbalang, five soil samples were collected from exposures on both flanks of Guyuk road; and another five samples were collected from exposures in the environs of Kwapukai village along Gombe road.

Random sampling method was adopted to cover a wide area where the black cotton soils were encountered. At each sampling point the thin topsoil was removed using a shovel and the B – horizon was collected at a depth of 20 to 25cm using pick axe and shovel. The samples were sun-dried at study base and packed in cellophane sample bags. Approximately, 8g of the representative samples were oven-dried at 60°C for two hours to remove the intergranular water, and then heated in a muffle furnace at 700°C for four hours to measure the structural water content at loss on ignition (LOI).

ii) Elemental Analysis

For the chemical tests, 1g of the dried sample was digested in a polypropylene bottle using a standard mixture of concentrated hydrofluoric acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid in a proportion of 7:1 respectively. The mixture was heated in a thermostatic water bath at 60°C for two (2) hours and the resultant milky sample solution was then cooled in a tightly closed bottle under tap. Afterwards 10ml of saturated boric acid was added to the solution and heated in the water bath at 70°C until a clear colourless sample solution was obtained. The clear solution was standardized to 250ml and used for the tests. Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometric method was used to determine iron oxide, soda and potash contents, and gravimetric method was used to determine silica content, while back titration with zinc acetate after addition of EDTA was employed to determine alumina, quick lime and magnesia contents. The chemical analysis was done at National Metallurgical Development Centre, Jos.

iii) Mineralogical Analysis

For the mineralogical tests, the samples were soaked in distilled water for 24 hours, disaggregated and sieved using 62 μ m mesh size. They were later dried, pulverized, and pelletized using pressed mounts. Mineralogical analysis of the sample pellets was done using XRD method, with the diffractograms recorded at a speed of 1°2 θ /cm/mm using copper tube anode radiation generated with 40kV and 55mA power supply. Observed diffraction traces were used to estimate quantities of the mineral species in the pulverized fraction. Peak heights of individual species were measured and values obtained were normalized to 100%. A Philips PW1800 diffractometer equipped with computerized counter and discriminator was used for the mineralogical analysis.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Results of the chemical analysis are given in Table 1. Concentrations of SiO₂ range from 48.7 – 54.7%, Al₂SiO₃ (14.7 – 19.8%), Fe₂O₃ (0.9 – 4.2%), CaO (0.9 – 1.9%), MgO (1.2 – 4.6%), Na₂O (0.4 – 1.5%) and K₂O (0.1 – 0.8%). The loss on ignition (LOI) ranges from 6.3 – 10.2%. Relatively, the Bembel soils have higher silica, alumina and iron but lower alkalis, lime and magnesia contents when compared with the Ngbalang and Kwapukai soil samples. It is deduced therefore, that cotton soils from weathered basaltic materials are largely siliceous while those from weathered shales are in addition, slightly Ca - enriched. This is probably a reflection of the constituent clay mineral composition.

The diffractogram of major mineral peaks is given in Fig 2. The dominant minerals in a representative sample from Ngbalang are montmorillonite (with a d-spacing of 9.38Å), illite (with d-spacing of 3.26Å) and quartz (with d = 1.08Å). Results indicate that montmorillonite constitutes about 89% of the mineral contents, illite about 9%, and quartz constitutes 1%. Relative to the chemical composition, the shale-derived Ngbalang and Kwapukai cotton soils would be more montmorillonitic [because Na, Ca and Mg usually occur with H₂O in the interlayer], while the high silica and iron contents in the basalt-derived Bembel soils would contribute to increase in quartz and illite.

Industrial Assessment

Montmorillonitic clays are widely used as drilling mud and as catalysts in the petroleum industry, as bonding material (in foundries, for pelletizing taconite and molding sands), and as suspension agent in chemical and metallurgical industries (Velde, 1992). For production of drilling mud and usage as suspension agent for medical purposes and coal purification, montmorillonitic clay with appreciable Na contents is required (Olphen, 1977). The high viscosity in Na – rich montmorillonitic clays makes them good suspension agents, hence are useful in chemical industry as fire retarders and in pharmaceutical industry as suspension media for medicinal tests. Fisk (1946) however submitted that clay materials used as suspension media must have at least 2.7% Na content. The studied clayey soils contain low (averagely 0.99%) sodium, hence cannot be used for these purposes. The high iron content (averagely 2.31%) of the studied montmorillonitic soils limits its use as catalyzing agent, which specifically requires clay materials with low (<0.15%) iron content (Velde, 1992). This high Fe contents can however, be partially removed by activation and the material calcined to develop its thermal stability for use as a catalyst (Olphen, 1977). However, the appreciable calcium and magnesium contents of the studied Ngbalang montmorillonitic soil make them suitable for use as decolorizer and absorbent materials (Grim, 1962). Generally, the Ca – rich montmorillonitic clays have better decolourizing and adsorbent property than the Na – rich variety. They are used to bleach colouring matter from oils and as adsorbent for chemical and pharmaceutical products. Also, the abundant (89%) montmorillonite minerals in the studied soil can provide the colloidal and electronegative properties required for purifiers used in clarifying turbid water and treatment of juice beverages.

CONCLUSION

The assessment of the chemical and mineralogical composition of the black cotton soils in some parts of the Yola basin has revealed that the weathered products from basaltic rocks are highly siliceous, iron-rich and contain less montmorillonite compared to those formed from weathered shales. On the basis of these characteristics, black cotton soils in Ngurore – Numan area can be used as decolorizer, absorbent materials

and as impermeable film in purifying materials owing to their low Na and high Ca, Mg and montmorillonite (about 89%) contents. It should be noted however, that the shale – derived Ngalang and Kwakpukai black cotton soils which are mainly Ca – montmorillonitic would serve these purposes better. The low sodium content in the soils limits their suitability for use as drilling mud. Considering the usefulness of black cotton soils, the authors strongly recommend further chemical and mineralogical examination and possibly, beneficiation studies on these cotton soils and similar deposits in other parts of Nigeria. Assessment of basic physical properties like flowability, absorption capacity and density of the soils will be carried out to measure their efficiency for use as bleaching agents. Also beneficiation studies to remove the illite and quartz contents in the soils and possibly convert the Ca-montmorillonite to Na-montmorillonite will be attempted to fully ascertain effective suitability of the soils for production of drilling mud.

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Table 1 Composition of studied Black Cotton soils

LOCATION/ SAMPLES		OXIDES (%)								MINERALS (%)		
		SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	LOI	Mont	Illite	Quartz
Bembel	1	53.1	18.4	4.2	1.4	4.0	1.1	0.8	10.0			
	2	51.9	17.6	2.9	1.0	3.2	0.9	0.3	9.1			
	3	48.7	16.1	2.3	1.0	1.3	0.4	0.1	6.3			
	4	54.7	19.8	1.7	0.9	3.3	0.8	0.4	7.5			
	5	52.3	18.9	2.1	1.4	2.3	1.2	0.3	8.0			
	Mean	52.1	18.2	2.7	1.2	2.8	1.3		8.3			
Ngbalang	6	50.5	17.2	1.9	1.7	2.1	1.1	0.3	10.0			
	7	49.2	16.6	0.9	0.9	1.9	0.8	0.2	7.5			
	8	48.9	15.2	1.7	0.9	1.6	0.6	0.1	6.9			
	9	50.4	16.7	3.1	1.1	3.4	1.1	0.2	7.5			
	10	52.6	14.9	2.9	1.6	2.9	1.3	0.7	6.9			
	Mean	50.3	16.1	1.9	1.3	2.4	1.3		7.8			
Kwakupakai	11	51.0	16.2	2.3	1.9	4.6	1.6	0.5	7.2			
	12	49.9	15.0	1.2	0.9	3.8	0.5	0.2	9.6			
	13	53.2	14.7	2.1	1.5	3.1	1.3	0.2	10.2			
	14	50.1	17.7	1.9	1.9	2.2	1.5	0.2	7.9			
	15	50.8	18.9	2.4	1.1	3.1	0.9	0.2	8.0			
	Mean	51.0	16.5	2.0	1.5	3.4	1.4		8.6			
Averages	A	52.1	18.2	2.7	1.2	2.8	1.3	8.3				
	B	50.7	16.3	1.9	1.4	2.9	1.3	8.2				
	C	51.4	17.3	2.3	1.3	2.9	1.3	8.3	89	9	1	
	D	55.4	20.1	3.7	0.5	2.5	1.7	14.7	-	-	-	

Note: A = Cotton soils from weathered basaltic rocks (from Bembel)
 B = Cotton soils from weathered shale rocks (from Ngbalang and Kwakupakai)
 C = Grand average for entire study area [A + B]/2
 D = Reference sample, bentonitic soils (Fisk, 1946)
 Mont = montmorillonite clay mineral
 LOI = Loss on ignition

Fig. 2. Typical diffractogram of the studied black cotton soils

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